

THE SENTENCE AND WORD ORDER IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article discusses about sentences in English, their types, functions and word order. The information about the topic is explained in a very clear and simple way.

Key words: Sentence, simple, compound, complex, compound-complex, declarative, interrogative, imperative, exclamatory, subject, predicate, object, attribute, adverbial modifier.

What is a sentence? **A sentence** is a group of words that expresses a complete idea.

✓ **Basic sentence structure**

There are 4 basic sentence structure in English.

- **A simple sentence** in a sentence with just one independent clause (also called main clause): Sadiya called.
- **A compound sentence** contains at least two independent clauses: Sadiya called and I answered.
- **A complex sentence** contains an independent clause and at least one dependent clause: Sadiya called me when I was working.
- **A compound-complex sentence** contains two or more independent clause and at least one dependent clause: Sadiya laughed and I called her when we opened the door.

✓ **Functional types of sentences**

There are 4 main types of sentences that can be distinguished by their function

and purpose.

- **A declarative sentence** makes a statement: We are moving to Tashkent.
- **An interrogative sentence** poses a question: Would you like to have tea or coffee?
- **An imperative sentence** gives instructions or expresses a request or demand:

Don't ever touch my phone. Please be quiet.

- **An exclamatory sentence** expresses strong feelings by making an explanation: What a large dog. Wow! I really can't believe we did that!

What are the different parts of a sentence?

The different parts of a sentence are subject, predicate, object, attribute and adverbial modifier. These different parts of a sentence can add variety to your writing style and depending on where you place each part, they can change the meaning of your words.

➤ **The subject**

Noun-subject: The teacher has come.

Pronoun-subject: He has written.

Infinitive-subject: To swim is pleasant.

Gerund-subject: Smoking is not allowed here.

Numeral-subject: "Seven" is my favourite number.

Any word used as a noun: "No" is her usual reply to any question.

➤ **The predicate**

Simple predicate: She works with me. She will return soon.

Compound predicate: He did homework and played video games.

My younger brother likes chicken but hates turkey.

Complete predicate: Link verb + noun/adj/num/pronoun/gerund/participle.

You look young and beautiful. My aim is learning English perfectly. It is mine.

- **Verb + verb. Modal verb + infinitive**

She may come at any time if she wants to learn English. You must look after her.

- **To be + adjective + infinitive**

I am glad to see you. He is ready to help me.

✓ **Secondary parts of the sentence.**

➤ **Object** in English is used to express to whom or what the action of the main predicate is directed. There are different types of object in English, including:

1. **Direct object** indicates who or what is performing the action expressed by the predicate : I understood her speaking and writing. He asked me to do it.
2. **Indirect object** indicates to whom or why the action expressed by the predicate is addressed. The indirect object precedes the direct object and can be a noun or a pronoun: I showed him the letter. He told us a funny story.
3. **Prepositional object.** In a sentence, the object of a preposition is a noun or pronoun that comes after a preposition: I spent a lot of money on books. We spoke about our work.

Subject + predicate	Indirect object	Direct object	Prepositional object
I gave	Him	a book	about computers

➤ **Attributes** usually defines a noun. The attribute doesn't have a permanent place in the sentence. It can determine any part of a sentence made from a noun phrase. Attributes can be expressed by:

1. **An adjective** (the most common way of expressing an attribute).

E.g: I am speaking about the big girl, not the little one.

2. **A pronoun** (possessive, defining, demonstrative ,interrogative).

E.g: What sports do you like best? He extended his hand to me.

3. **A numeral** (cardinal or ordinal).

E.g: ten-year old girl won the prize. The second book has been written.

4. A noun: in common case

E.g: The town library is closed on Sundays. I like chicken soap.

In possessive case: The teacher corrected the student’s mistakes.

➤ **Adverbial modifier.** The part of the sentence that shows how and in what way (where, when, why) the action took place is called adverbial modifier.

She will come soon. I found her in the garden. I came to see her. He spoke slowly.

Adverbial modifier can be formed from adverb, prepositional noun, participle, infinitives and prepositional gerunds.

On arriving at the station he saw his teacher.

While **reading** the book I came across a number of interesting expressions.

He **quickly** opened the door.

Subject + Verb + Object	Adverbial modifier of manner	Adverbial modifier of place	Adverbial modifier of time
I met her	by chance	at the theatre	a few days ago

Word order

Subject	Predicate	Object			Adverbial modifier		
		indirect	direct	prepositional	of manner	of place	of time
We	sent	the buyers	the documents			yesterday	
We	met		her		by chance	at the market today	

In conclusion, the topic of the sentence and word order in English is very comprehensive. In this article, we briefly touched the parts of the English sentences, their functions and order of the sentence. I believe that this information

will serve as a great source of knowledge for everyone.

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